

2013 Scholarly Forum

**Diversity and Multicultural Education Aspects of
the North Dakota K-12 Public Schools**

Technology and Multicultural Education

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Tuesday March 5th, 2013

Assertion

In order to decrease the multicultural challenges, the educational system of North Dakota pays special attention and efforts on developing and employing technology into classrooms.

Themes

1- The K-12 schools innovate and create some multicultural strategies and techniques that maximize the effectiveness of teaching and learning process in multicultural classrooms.

Themes

2- The K-12 schools in north Dakota employ some specific enabling technologies that maximize the engagement and collaborating in multicultural learning environments.

Categories

1- Principles and directions of using technology in enhancing multicultural education

Categories

2- Hardware and software that influence the diverse multicultural learning environment

Codes

- High-qualified staff
- Organizing their priorities and specific needs
- Building attractive learning environment
- High-level of verbal and non-verbal communication
- Creating more multicultural activities

“Technology is related to a couple things, I think from the internet stand point, there are a lot of easy ways to have connection with different palaces .. so you can have a sister or brother schools from different countries and you can talk about different topics and you can see their perspectives about the topic connection with different palaces.”

Codes

- Co-teachers
- Different levels of motivations
- Prior expectations and judgments
- Well-designed extra activities
- Bridging the cultural gap
- Sharing different ideas and perspectives

“And the other thing if you have other one from other certain background, you can use the online connection”

Codes

- Internet and distance connection
- Social networks
- Facebook groups
- Twitter
- Google+
- Skype
- MSN and Yahoo messengers
- Academic, social, and scientific forums
- YouTube channel
- Email and electronic letters
- Electronic platforms

"For instance, the schools have group pages on Facebook and students can share pictures, posts, videos, and other activities. It just makes that connection so much easier."

Codes

- Desktops, Laptops, and i pads
- Cell phones and I phones
- Texting, calls, and sharing media
- Video conference and online connection
- Audio-video-text functions
- Watching videos about different cultures
- Getting translation for these videos

“Facebook for instance that connections could be made .. if two classrooms has Facebook pages from different countries, they could post up pictures and know the activities, the classes, the cultures.. it just makes that connection so much easier .. so you know .. all these social connections bring in you know .. bring people together witch is the purpose of these things and part of it key to the success social connections.”

Codes

- Integrated technology
- International TV media
- Local TV media
- Communication technology and divergent ELL classrooms
- Online and electronic dictionaries

“I think all these tools could help and be useful .. I think the challenge is just understanding getting accepted from other students in the classroom .. I think the acceptance is important to see other culture and spectrums. They could do that on Google, they could do that on YouTube, they could do that form all other tools .. but what they are doing with that getting accepted from other?”

Thank you very much for watching!

